

Training materials to train the trainers in reaching 100% organic seed

Authors: Ilsa Phillips (IFOAM OE), Caroline Formont (IFOAM OE), Kaja Gutzen (FiBL DE), Gabriele Maneo (EC-LLD), Mariano Iossa (FiBL Europe), Stephanie Mothes (ITAB), Francesca Gori (RSR), Freya Schäfer (FiBL DE)

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Contact	Freya Schäfer, freya.schaefer@fibl.org

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LiveSeeding - Organic seed and plant breeding to accelerate sustainable and diverse food systems in Europe is a 4-year Innovation Action funded by the European Union, the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). The project started in October 2022 and brings together 37 organisations operating in 16 European countries. LiveSeeding provides science-based evidence and best practice solutions to help achieve 100 % organic seed.

LiveSeeding contributes to the transition towards environmentally-friendly, climate-neutral, healthy and fair food systems through a **PUSH-PULL-ENABLE strategy** to

- enhance the availability and adequacy of organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PUSH),
- increase and stabilise the market demand for organic seeds of cultivars appropriate to organic farming (PULL),
- foster an enabling policy and regulatory environment where both demand and supply can harmoniously and productively negotiate without irrelevant constraints due to legal restrictions and/or regulatory fragmentation (ENABLE).

LiveSeeding addresses the topics in a **holistic multi-actor, multi-stakeholder, participatory approach** involving stakeholders along the value chain in 17 local **Living Labs (LLs)** and 3 established networks of organic breeders (**ECO-PB**), seed savers (**ECLLD**) and Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (**MUFPP**). 15 European countries cover the different pedoclimatic zones and socio-economic contexts, including countries with a low level of development in organic seed and breeding in East and South Europe.

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List of abbreviations

EU	European Union
PRM	Plant Reproductive Material
RDB	EU Router Database
ToT	Training of trainers

Summary

*This training manual is designed for **national authorities and seed experts** across the EU, with the goal of **strengthening their capacities and promoting transparency, knowledge exchange, and harmonized implementation** of the EU organic regulation.*

The LiveSeeding project seeks to improve the availability and adequacy of organic seeds of cultivars tailored to organic farming systems, using a "push-pull-enable" approach. National authorities and organic seed stakeholders play a key role in reducing the reliance on non-organic seeds and planting material, which are still used under derogations in organic agriculture. Strengthening their capacities is therefore essential to address the limited availability and inconsistent listing of organic seeds in national databases.

The training of trainers (ToT) materials are organized into four modules, each consisting of a few units:

Module 19 guides **national authorities and seed experts** in preparing for the EU's 2036 **phase-out of non-organic seed use** in organic agriculture. It is structured into 4 units:

- (1) introduction to Plant Reproductive Material (PRM) legislation and its relevance for organic farming,*
- (2) the role of national and EU-wide databases in improving market transparency and seed availability,*
- (3) lessons from Member States on designing national roadmaps with stakeholder engagement, incentives, and monitoring, and*
- (4) practical groundwork for developing a national roadmap through stakeholder mapping, data collection, and prioritization of key actions.*

Module 20 provides self-paced training for **suppliers of organic and in-conversion seeds to list their offers in national databases via the EU Router Database (RDB)**. The training includes instructional videos, guides, and FAQs covering registration, offer management, and communication with authorities. The aim is to simplify the listing process, improve data accuracy, and increase the availability and visibility of organic seed across the EU.

Module 21 is a self-paced training course designed for **national authorities managing organic seed databases** in the EU. It aims to **build their capacity to use the European Router Database (RDB)** to integrate and manage supplier offers more efficiently. The training includes step-by-step videos, guides, and FAQs on registration, offer validation, species categorisation, data export, and communication with suppliers. The module supports both authorities using automated API connections and those relying on manual processes, contributing to a more robust and transparent EU-wide organic seed system.

Module 22 offers a **replicable training model focused on the reform of EU seed marketing legislation and its impact on seed diversity and farmer-led seed systems**. It targets small-scale farmers, seed networks, and advocacy groups, and aims to build their capacity to analyze policy developments, reflect on their practical implications and explore strategies for engagement. Through interactive units including presentations, group discussions, and action planning, the module helps participants understand the legal landscape, identify advocacy opportunities, and collaborate across stakeholder networks to shape inclusive seed policies.

Each training module includes a comprehensive training outline that clearly defines the scope of the training, the learning objectives and intended audience, the instructional methods and formats, as well as the materials used and the assessment approach. This outline has been created by experts in training methodology and design, serving as a standardized framework for all training content and related deliverables within the project.

1.1 Justification, scope and main objectives

In the context of the EU's goal to phase out derogations for non-organic plant reproductive material (PRM) by 2036, increasing the supply and uptake of organic seeds is a priority for the organic farming sector. However, limited availability and inconsistent listing of organic seed across national databases pose a significant barrier. Reducing the use of non-organic seed and planting material is critical to strengthening the integrity and sustainability of organic farming systems.

However, this goal cannot be achieved without targeted capacity building among key stakeholders, including seed suppliers, farmers, national authorities and certification bodies. Many actors in the organic sector still face practical, technical or regulatory challenges in producing, offering, accessing or monitoring organic seeds. Capacity building helps address these challenges by equipping stakeholders with the knowledge, skills, and tools needed to operate effectively within the evolving legal and market frameworks.

The aim of task 4.5 is to provide training to stimulate transparency, knowledge exchange and harmonisation of implementation of the organic regulation across Eu countries.

Deliverable D4.2 contributes to the objective of this task by collecting training materials and creating a learning and capacity building path that can be reused and replicated.

For **seed suppliers**, training can improve their ability to list and manage organic seed offers in national and EU-wide databases, increasing visibility and availability. For **farmers**, it enables a better understanding of seed sourcing requirements and encourages the use of organic varieties adapted to organic conditions. For **national authorities**, capacity building ensures consistent implementation of EU regulations, enhances database management, and reduces reliance on derogations.

By offering freely accessible online training, participants can become trainers themselves, sharing knowledge with colleagues to extend the outreach and achieve greater impact. Ultimately, empowering all stakeholders through education, technical support, and collaboration strengthens the entire organic seed system, increases transparency and accelerates the transition toward full organic seed use. Ultimately, it contributes to the long-term goals of organic agriculture in the EU.

The scope of the training work of T4.5 and the present deliverable is being set on the basis of the recommendations of the LIVESEED project (EU funded project, on whose results and work LiveSeeding was built on).

As shown in the EU funded project [LIVESEED](#), the organic seed supply, including organic farm saved seed, is covering on average less than 50% of the organic farm area with great differences between crops and countries¹. Also, the perception of farmers towards organic seed use varies among countries, marketing strategy and farm size². A lack of information about availability and price for organic seed is likely to act as a barrier to investment³. Therefore, it will be essential to take the necessary strategic steps at the national level to reach this goal of increasing the supply and demand of organic plant reproductive material (PRM).

LIVESEED project recommended that capacity building activities should focus on:

- 1) the maintenance and development of the national organic seed databases and its connection to the EU-wide Router Database (see notably Module 3 of this deliverable),
- 2) the establishment or strengthened Organic Seed Expert Group at national level,
- 3) exchange on possible incentives to increase supply and demand for organic seeds,
- 4) collecting (national) data on the use of organic, non-organic and farm-saved PRM,
- 5) establish a decision framework for a non-derogation list,
- 6) develop a national roadmap towards 100% organic seed use, including action points and intermediate goals.

¹ Petitti M, Ortolani L, Schäfer F, Messmer M. The State of Organic Seed in Europe. LIVESEED. November 2019, updated January 2021. https://www.liveseed.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Booklet2-LIVESEED_2021_web.pdf

² Orsini S, Costanzo A, Solfanelli F, Zanoli R, Padel S, Messmer MM, Winter E, Schaefer F. Factors Affecting the Use of Organic Seed by Organic Farmers in Europe. *Sustainability*. 2020; 12(20):8540. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12208540>

³ Padel S, Orsini S, Solfanelli F, Zanoli R. Can the Market Deliver 100% Organic Seed and Varieties in Europe? *Sustainability*. 2021; 13(18):10305. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su131810305>

1.2 Training methodology, structure and modules description

This deliverable is organized in four modules; each organized in one or several units. Each training module includes a comprehensive training outline that clearly defines the scope of the training, the learning objectives and intended audience, the instructional methods and formats, as well as the materials used and the assessment approach.

- **Module 19** provides national authorities and seed experts with the foundation and practical tools needed to prepare for the EU's goal of phasing out non-organic seed use by 2036. It addresses current challenges such as limited availability, low transparency, and uneven adoption of organic seeds, while guiding participants on how to build effective national strategies. By covering legislation, databases, best practices, and roadmap design, the module ensures that countries can set clear priorities, engage stakeholders, and establish concrete steps towards achieving 100% organic seed use in a structured and coordinated way.
- **Module 20** addresses this by aiming to strengthen the capacity of organic seed suppliers to effectively use the European Router Database (RDB), a central platform that connects national databases. By enabling suppliers to submit and manage their offers in multiple Member States through a single interface, the RDB reduces administrative burden, improves visibility of organic seed, and ensures compliance with EU and national regulations. The objective of the module is to equip suppliers with the necessary knowledge and tools to use the RDB efficiently, ultimately contributing to a more robust and transparent organic seed market in the EU.
- **Module 21** addresses this challenge by focusing on the role of national authorities, who are responsible for maintaining and expanding organic seed listings in their national systems. The justification for this training lies in the need to equip authorities with practical skills to manage supplier data, validate offers, and ensure regulatory compliance using the European Router Database (RDB). By strengthening the capacity of authorities to fully utilize the RDB—whether through API connections or manual export functions, the objective is to streamline offer integration, improve database accuracy, and enlarge organic seed supply across the EU. This will help

reduce the reliance on non-organic PRM and promote transparency and trust in the organic seed market.

- **Module 22** addresses the ongoing reform of the EU seed marketing legislation which carries significant implications for seed diversity, small-scale farmers, and civil society actors involved in agroecology and biodiversity conservation. As these regulatory changes can either constrain or empower alternative seed systems, there is a pressing need to build the capacity of stakeholders to understand, critically assess, and influence this policy process. This module provides a structured training approach to equip participants—from seed savers to advocacy groups—with the necessary knowledge and tools to engage meaningfully in the reform. The objective is to foster strategic thinking, strengthen collective action, and promote inclusive legislation that supports diverse seed systems, farmer autonomy, and sustainable agriculture in the EU and beyond.

The development of the common training outline and learning methodology was led by **Stéphanie Mothes (ITAB, France)** and **Mariano Iossa (FiBL Europe)**, with support from **Francesca Gori (RSR IT)**, as part of the work carried out by the Training Task Force (T7.2).

1.3 Training Modules

3.1 Module 19 - Implementing a roadmap towards 100% organic seed use by 2036

Topics

The European Commission plans to phase out all derogations for the use of non-organic seeds in organic agriculture by the end of 2036. Capacity building is needed to support national authorities in this process to achieve the phasing-out and to create transparency for the organic seed market.

This module covers in particular the last point of the recommendations of the LIVESEED project (see the last paragraph of chapter 1, recommendation “6. develop a national roadmap towards 100% organic seed use, including action points and intermediate goals”), notably by drawing on the experience of other Member States.

Target groups

National authorities and seed experts with the competences working on in the organic agriculture department or the seed and breeding department, and those responsible for implementing the Organic Regulation, to increase the supply and demand for organic seed and phase out the use of non-organic seed/PRM.

Learning objectives

This self-paced training is designed to help national authorities in increasing the supply and demand of organic PRM in their national contexts, notably by drawing on best practices from European Member States that have already implemented roadmaps or plan to achieve such objective.

Units

Unit 1: Introduction to the PRM legislation (30 min).

Understanding the regulatory context is the first step to understanding what the rules are to comply with. Namely, participants are invited to review the [LIVESEED policy recommendations](#) for national and regional authorities to implement the organic

regulation to increase production and use of organic seed and the report on the Plant Reproductive Material (PRM) legislation developments, to understand what is at stake for the organic sector (see: [New patented GMOs, seed marketing reform: An attack on peasant agriculture in Europe](#)). Both reports are material for reading to get into the topic.

Participants should note that this report was published in 2020 so the [Organic Regulation \(EU\) 2018/848](#) has entered into force since then. For more details on the regulatory background, participants can refer to Module 4 of this deliverable on Regulatory issues related to organic seed and breeding.

Unit 2: Organic PRM databases (2,5 hours)

To explore the role of organic PRM databases in supporting the development of a more transparent and accessible organic seed market, the video "[Exchange on organic seed and planting material databases – practice examples from Spain and Austria](#)" illustrate how different countries are implementing and improving their databases. Further resources provided in this deliverable in Module 20 and 21 (Using the EU Router database to enlarge organic seed supply in national databases) will help participants to understand the importance of the EU Router Database and how it can be used to strengthen national systems and increase the availability of organic seeds.

Unit 3: National roadmap projects to reach 100% organic seed (3 hours)

Now that the regulatory background and role of databases is set, this unit will focus specifically on how to design and implement national roadmaps. Documents from the LIVESEED and LiveSeeding projects should be read to understand the key elements for establishing a national plan, including stakeholder involvement, intermediate goals and monitoring tools:

- [Deliverable 4.1 on 'Updated and improved roadmap/ decision tree to reach 100% organic seed' \(2025\)](#).
- [LIVESEED Policy Brief: A national roadmap towards 100% organic seed \(2021\)](#).
- [LIVESEED Boosting organic seed and breeding across Europe: recommendations for stakeholders and policy makers \(2021\)](#)
- Watch the first part of the online conference "[Pathways to create a level playing field in the European organic seed sector](#)" dedicated to the implementation of seed expert group.

- Review the cross-country exchange reports ([May 2024](#), [June 2025](#) video also available [here](#))

Unit 4: From Knowledge to Action – Laying the Groundwork for a National Roadmap (2 hours)

Building on the previous units, this final unit encourages participants to take the first concrete steps toward drafting a national roadmap:

1. Stakeholder mapping: identify key stakeholders relevant to the development and implementation of a roadmap toward 100% organic seed use.
2. Data gathering: Identify what national data is already available and what is missing regarding: the production, demand, and use of organic seeds, derogations statistics.
3. First steps toward a Roadmap: based on previous units, list 3–5 priority actions that could be part of a national roadmap.

Learning material: Each unit has different training material, from recordings, presentations to reports.

1.4 Module 20 – Offering organic seed in the EU Router Database (RDB)

Topic

Each EU Member State is required to maintain a regularly updated national database on the national availability of organic and in-conversion seed and other plant reproductive material (PRM). Limited availability and inconsistent listings of organic PRM increase the risk of derogation misuse, allowing non-organic PRM to be sold at lower costs. To ensure a successful phase-out of derogations by 2036, it is crucial that all organic PRM is accurately represented in these national databases.

Since 2021, the RDB (www.seeds4organic.eu or www.plants4organic.eu) has served as a central platform connecting national databases. The RDB simplifies the process for suppliers by allowing them to submit PRM offers once for distribution across multiple national databases. This reduces administrative burden and enhances market visibility. National authorities can efficiently manage supplier registrations and offers through API connections or manual downloads. While the RDB is optional for Member States, it offers significant advantages, including improved efficiency and greater transparency in organic PRM management.

The RDB operates on a Background/Front-end model. Suppliers and authorities manage offers and documentation through the RDB, while farmers and control bodies access national databases to check availability or request derogations. Additionally, the RDB functions as a central repository, enhancing transparency in derogation practices and species categorisation.

In 2026, the RDB will be relaunched with new tools and improved functionalities. This self-paced training is designed to provide suppliers with the flexibility to learn and practice using the RDB at their own pace, and support colleagues by acting as trainers within their teams.

Target groups

Suppliers of organic and in-conversion PRM who wish to display their offers in one or more national databases across the EU and beyond (Switzerland, Iceland, UK).

The course address new users as well as already registered users who want to deepen their knowledge of offer management, explore different scenarios or address specific questions on key functionalities.

Learning objectives

This self-paced training is designed to equip participants with the knowledge and tools to effectively use the relaunched RDB to offer organic PRM.

The course covers all key functionalities, including placing and managing offers in national databases via the RDB, while ensuring compliance with EU and national requirements.

The course provides flexibility through written guides, FAQs and step-by-step instructional videos. Participants can progress at their own pace by engaging with the materials in a way that suits their learning style. For example, they can watch a video while simultaneously following the steps in their own RDB account to practice the steps in real time.

Units

Unit 1 Introduction and overview (30 min)

Gain a clear understanding of the RDB's role, its key functionalities and benefits for suppliers and authorities. Get to know the new public features: a central repository for annual national derogation reports and the national species/sub-species categorisation by Categories I to III. Watch the introductory video, covering the role of the RDB in market transparency, its key functionalities and the benefits it offers for suppliers and authorities.

The video [Online Training on the European Router Database for suppliers of organic seed and vegetative planting material](#) provides a first overview on the database and the practise abstract [European Router Database: centralised platform for suppliers of organic plant reproductive material \(PRM\)](#) explains the general functionality of the router database.

Further videos are available in the folder [Organic Eprints - Module 20 – Offering organic seed in the EU Router Database \(RDB\)](#).

Unit 2 Registration and application (1 hour)

Learn how to register as a supplier, applying to national authorities for listing approval, managing required documents such as organic certificates. Watch the video demonstrating the registration process, how to apply to national authorities for listing approval, and how to manage required documents such as organic certificates. Use written guides and FAQs to detail the process and help troubleshooting common

issues. Follow along in the RDB account to complete the registration and application process.

Unit 3 Placing and managing offers (2 hours)

Learn how to submit offers to one or multiple national databases via the RDB, updating and managing offers to ensure accuracy. Get to know new features such as providing extended offer and cultivar information. Watch the video explaining how to submit offers to one or multiple national databases via the RDB, and how to update and manage offers. Optionally, watch an additional 10-minute video with exemplary scenarios (e.g., different species, mixtures and qualities of PRM). Use written guides and FAQs to detail the process and help troubleshooting common issues. Follow along in the RDB account to practice submitting and managing offers.

Unit 4 Communication with national authorities (30 min)

Learn how to engage with authorities through the RDB for offer approvals, queries and updates. Watch the video on how to engage with national authorities through the RDB. Use written guides and FAQs to detail the process and help troubleshooting common issues. Follow along in the RDB account to initiate communication with national authorities.

Unit 5 Feedback (30 min)

Complete the feedback survey to identify areas for improvement, including suggestions for additional FAQs.

Learning material

The learning materials include videos, written guides, and FAQs. All instructional content will be freely accessible online via the RDB website.

- **Written guides and FAQs:** Step-by-step manuals detailing key functionalities including registration, offer placement, and communication with authorities. These guides will include screenshots and explanations for each process.
- **Instructional videos:** Short, easy-to-follow videos demonstrating each key step in the database. The videos will showcase different scenarios, including how to place offers for different species, mixtures and qualities of PRM, helping users to understand different contexts and requirements.

- **Feedback surveys:** A survey to collect feedback on the training process, helping to improve future versions and materials by addressing gaps, common misunderstandings, or requests for additional support.

The training material is not yet available, as new features of the RDB are currently being developed within the scope of the LiveSeeding project. The relaunched RDB is expected to go live in mid-January 2026. Accordingly, the training material will be adapted to reflect the new functionalities and will be available in the folder [Organic Eprints - Module 20 – Offering organic seed in the EU Router Database \(RDB\)](#).

1.5 Module 21 – Using the EU Router Database (RDB) to enlarge organic seed supply in national databases

Topic

Each EU Member State is required to maintain a regularly updated national database on the national availability of organic and in-conversion seed and other plant reproductive material (PRM). Limited availability and inconsistent listings of organic PRM increase the risk of derogation misuse, allowing non-organic PRM to be sold at lower costs. To ensure a successful phase-out of derogations by 2036, it is crucial that all organic PRM is accurately represented in these national databases.

Since 2021, the RDB (www.seeds4organic.eu or www.plants4organic.eu) has served as a central platform connecting national databases. The RDB simplifies the process for national authorities to manage offers from suppliers across multiple countries to enlarge national organic PRM supply, while ensuring compliance with EU and national requirements. Authorities play a critical role in maintaining the integrity and functionality of the RDB by managing supplier registrations, offer listings, ensuring the accuracy of data, and overseeing species categorisation.

The RDB operates on a Background/Front-end model. Suppliers and authorities manage offers and documentation through the RDB, while farmers and control bodies access national databases to check availability or request derogations. Additionally, the RDB functions as a central repository, enhancing transparency in derogation practices and species categorisation.

In 2026, the RDB will be relaunched with new tools and improved functionalities. This self-paced training is designed to provide national authorities with the flexibility to learn and practice using the RDB at their own pace, and support colleagues by acting as trainers within their teams.

Target groups

National authorities responsible for managing national database systems, including experienced users of the RDB who want to deepen their knowledge and new users.

The course addresses both authorities with API connections between their national database and the RDB as well as authorities without an API, who rely on the manual export function to transfer offers to national database.

Learning objectives

This self-paced training is designed to equip participants with the knowledge and tools to effectively use the relaunched RDB to enlarge the organic PRM supply in national databases.

This course covers all key functionalities, including managing suppliers and their offers in national databases via the RDB, while ensuring compliance with EU and national requirements.

The course provides flexibility through written guides, FAQs and step-by-step instructional videos. Participants can progress at their own pace by engaging with the materials in a way that suits their learning style. For example, they can watch a video while simultaneously following the steps in their own RDB account to practice the steps in real time.

Units

Unit 1 Introduction and overview (1,5 hours)

The gain a clear understanding of the RDB's role, its key functionalities and benefits for suppliers and authorities the report ["Online Policy Conference - Pathways to create a level playing field in the organic seed sector in the EU"](#) as well as the two videos ["Online Training on the European Router Database for EU Member State national authorities"](#) and ["Exchange on organic seed and planting material databases: Router database & organicXseeds – Functions, challenges, new features"](#) provide a first overview.

To get to know the new features further materials will be available in the folder [Organic Eprints - Module 21 – Using the EU Router Database \(RDB\) to enlarge organic seed supply in national databases](#). The new features integrate a central repository for annual national derogation reports and the national species/sub-species categorisation by Categories I to III. Watch the introductory video, covering the role of the RDB in market transparency, its key functionalities and the benefits it offers for suppliers and authorities.

Unit 2 Registration (30 min)

Learn how to register as an authority and exploring account management options. Watch the video demonstrating the registration process and account management options. Use written guides and FAQs to detail the process and help troubleshooting common issues. Follow along in the RDB account to complete the registration process.

Unit 3 Supplier and offer management (1 hour)

Learn how to manage supplier applications and PRM offers submitted to national databases via the RDB. Watch the video on managing supplier applications and PRM offers submitted to national databases via the RDB. Optionally, watch an additional 10-minute video with exemplary scenarios (e.g., different species, mixtures and qualities of PRM). Use written guides and FAQs to detail the process and help troubleshooting common issues. Follow along in the RDB account to process supplier applications and manage offers.

Unit 4 Species and variety group management (1 hour)

Learn how to manage and categorise species and variety groups. Watch the video explaining on managing species and variety groups, including defining and categorising variety groups according to EU regulations, allocating varieties, and adding informational texts to species. Use written guides and FAQs to detail the process and help troubleshooting common issues. Follow along in the RDB account.

Unit 5 Export functions (1 hour)

Learn how to use the RDB export tools to generate reports for internal use or submission to the European Commission. Get to know the possibility of setting up an API (Application Programming Interface) to the national organic seed database for automatic offer transmission. Watch the video explaining on using RDB export tools to generate reports for internal use, upload in national database system or submission to the European Commission. Use written guides and FAQs to detail the process and help troubleshooting common issues. Follow along in the RDB account to complete the export of offers.

Unit 6 Communication with suppliers (30 min)

Learn how to engage with suppliers through the RDB for offer approvals, queries and updates. Watch the video on how to engage with suppliers through the RDB. Use written guides and FAQs to detail the process and help troubleshooting common issues. Follow along in the RDB account to initiate communication with suppliers.

Unit 7 Feedback (30 min)

Complete the feedback survey to identify areas for improvement, including suggestions for additional FAQs.

Learning material

The learning materials include videos, written guides, and FAQs. All instructional content will be freely accessible online via the RDB website.

- **Written guides and FAQs:** Step-by-step manuals detailing key functionalities including registration, supplier and offer management, and communication with suppliers. These guides will include screenshots and explanations for each process.
- **Instructional videos:** Short, easy-to-follow videos demonstrating each key step in the database. The videos will showcase different scenarios, including how to manage offers of different species, mixtures and qualities of PRM, helping users to understand different contexts and requirements.
- **Feedback surveys:** A survey to collect feedback on the training process, helping to improve future versions and materials by addressing gaps, common misunderstandings, or requests for additional support.

The training material is not yet available, as new features of the RDB are currently being developed within the scope of the LiveSeeding project. The relaunched RDB is expected to go live in mid-January 2026. Accordingly, the training material will be adapted to reflect the new functionalities and will be available in the folder [Organic Eprints - Module 21 – Using the EU Router Database \(RDB\) to enlarge organic seed supply in national databases.](#)

1.6 Module 22 - Regulatory issues related to organic seed and breeding

Topic

This module provides a structured training approach to strengthen the capacity of civil society actors, seed networks, and farmer organisations to follow regulatory processes, critically assess proposed reforms, and identify strategic opportunities for advocacy and policy engagement. It focuses on developing participants' ability to understand the implications of legal frameworks for seed systems, connect technical and political dimensions, and collaborate effectively to influence change.

The training uses the ongoing reform of the EU seed marketing legislation as a central case study. This reform process, launched in 2023, has significant implications for how farmers, seed savers, and small-scale seed enterprises can access, exchange, and conserve agricultural biodiversity and organic seeds. While the proposed legislation may introduce restrictions on traditional seed practices, it also opens up opportunities to advocate for more inclusive, diverse, and decentralised seed systems, particularly if stakeholders are well-informed and coordinated.

Piloted through in-person sessions during the Let's Liberate Diversity! Forums in 2023 and 2024, the module offers a tested and replicable framework for training that combines technical knowledge with strategic reflection and peer exchange. Although centered on the EU seed reform, the approach is designed to be adapted to other regulatory contexts related to seed laws and legislation.

By the end of the training, participants will be equipped with skills and capacity not only to understand and assess the specific reform examined, but also to apply the methodology to future legislative developments and engage in coordinated policy dialogue.

Target Groups

This training is designed for a diverse range of actors engaged in seed diversity and organic seeds. It is particularly relevant for small-scale farmers and seed savers involved in the conservation and exchange of plant genetic resources, as well as representatives of seed networks, farmers' organisations, and civil society coalitions.

The module also addresses the needs of advocacy practitioners and campaigners working at local, national, or EU levels who are seeking to better understand and influence seed policy processes.

Participants are expected to have a beginner to intermediate level of familiarity with seed policy. The training model is flexible and can be used to support peer learning, internal organisational capacity building, coalition development, or mobilisation around advocacy initiatives.

Learning Objectives

By the end of the training, participants will have strengthened their capacity to follow regulatory processes, assess proposed reforms in relation to their work, and identify opportunities for advocacy and collaboration. They will understand the rationale, scope, and key elements of the EU seed marketing reform, and be able to critically reflect on how seed laws shape the rights, practices, and constraints faced by small-scale seed producers.

Participants will be equipped to analyse the potential impacts of legislative changes—particularly with respect to seed exchange, market access, and cultivated diversity—and to identify strategic entry points for engagement. The training will also support them in exploring pathways for advocacy at national and European levels, formulating relevant messages and actions to influence policy outcomes, and strengthening collaboration across networks and stakeholder groups.

Units

Unit 1: Understanding the Legislative Context and State of Play (30 min)

This introductory unit provides participants understanding of the EU legislative process and the key features of the proposed reform of the EU Regulation on the Production and Marketing of Plant Reproductive Material (PRM). Through reading a preparatory handout [Handout 1: EU Legislative Processes and Institutions](#), participants explore how EU institutions interact in shaping policy, the timeline of the reform, and the key elements of its content. This resource helps clarify the structure of the legislative process and the implications of the reform for seed systems. The session concludes with an open Q&A to ensure clarity on the reform's scope and terminology.

Unit 2: Analysing Impacts on Seed Systems and Diversity (40 min)

In this session, participants reflect on how the proposed reform could affect their practices, including seed exchanges, the activities of seed networks, and community seed initiatives. Using a structured analysis with the support of the [Handout 2 : Analysis of the EU Seed Marketing Reform from a Seed Diversity Perspective](#), they explore institutional positions (European Commission, Parliament, and Council) and their expected impact on key issues such as farmers' rights, market access, and diversity-friendly practices. The handout provides an in-depth analysis of the EU seed marketing reform, developed from a seed diversity and farmers' rights perspective, offers participants a critical understanding of the reform's likely impacts. The document highlights the positions of the European Commission, Parliament, and Council, and assesses their implications for conservation varieties, farmer seed exchanges, and the rights enshrined in UNDROP.

Unit 3: Exploring Advocacy Pathways and Building Alliances (30 min)

This unit focuses on strategic action. Participants identify opportunities to engage in advocacy at the national and EU levels, including direct engagement with ministries, petitions, media campaigns, and joint statements. The session encourages mapping of potential alliances and coordination mechanisms to influence the legislative outcome and protect diversity-friendly approaches. The reading material [Handout 3: Examples of Opportunities for Engagement in the EU Seed Reform](#) provides participants with examples of strategic advocacy actions, including direct engagement with agricultural ministries, petition mobilisation, joint statements, and coordination across Member States.

Unit 4: Group Reporting and Collective Synthesis (10 min)

Each group presents its key insights, proposed actions, or advocacy entry points. The session concludes with a plenary synthesis and discussion of possible next steps for participants to adapt the methodology in their own contexts or campaigns. The wrap-up draws from examples presented at the Let's Liberate Diversity! Forum in Antibes.

For further readings, the slides of the Capacity-building seminar, ECLLD Forum Dublin, 27. October 2023 are provided in this folder [Organic Eprints - Module 22 - Regulatory issues related to organic seed and breeding](#).

4. Materials

The materials available for each Module include:

- The Training Outline summarizing concepts and learning objectives for each training module;
- The corresponding presentations for each unit;
- The additional materials suggested in the presentations intended to widen the learning process (i) papers, ii) online available tutorials, iii) links to online available software and simulators, iv) links to projects, etc.);
- The recordings of the courses, with the lecturers explaining in a dynamic way the different units, answering questions, solving the quizzes in common discussion, proposing activities and homework.

These materials are available in Organic EPrints to ensure accessibility in the long term. Links are listed in table 1.

Table 1. List of training materials available in Organic EPrints repository.

	Links to Organic EPrints
Module 19	https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56161/
Module 20	https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56164/
Module 21	https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56165/
Module 22	https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56166/

5 . Outreach

The work of WP4, task T4.5 and of deliverable D4.2 is based on a series of meetings and trainings that took place during the project. Here a list of such meetings and trainings:

Date	Module	Title	Link	Participants
25 Jan 2023	M19 and M21	Online Policy Conference - Pathways to create a level playing field in the organic seed sector in the EU: More transparency through the Router database & organicXseeds	Organic Eprints - Report on the Online Policy Conference „Pathways to create a level playing field in the organic seed sector in the EU“	95
16 Mar 2023	M21	Online Training on the European Router Database (www.seeds4organic.eu) for EU Member State national authorities	https://youtu.be/nrsmg-vFn2c	47
23 Mar 2023	M20	Online Training on the European Router Database (www.seeds4organic.eu) for suppliers of organic seed and vegetative planting material	https://youtu.be/5CaVWEtMTao	57
4 Jul 2024	M21	Exchange on organic seed and planting material databases: Router database & organicXseeds – Functions, challenges, new features	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fQD1V8zRRxY	39
27 Oct 2023	M22	LLD Forum 2023 (Dublin) Capacity Building on EU Seed Marketing Reform	Liveseeding introduction: https://liberatediversity.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/Capacity-building-on-seed-marketing-reform-	14

			Liveseeding-introduction-1.pdf Presentation of the EU seed reform: https://liberatediversity.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/09/Capacity-building-on-seed-marketing-reform-Overview-of-the-reform-content.pdf	
04 Oct 2024	M22	LLD Forum 2024 (Antibes) Capacity Building Workshop: All you ever wanted to know on EU Seed Law	Notes from the session: https://docs.google.com/document/d/19ILP7ES4IFveSSA4iiPnOfwbncIBckc9/edit?usp=sharing&ouid=102519996991625553340&rtpof=true&sd=true	30
18 Nov 2024	M20	PRACTICE ABSTRACT European Router Database: centralised platform for suppliers of organic plant reproductive material (PRM)	https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/54316/	
5 June	M19	LiveSeeding online webinar 'Developing roadmaps to improve the supply of organically produced seed and planting material until 2036 in Germany	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cKMMFXX0qew&embeds_referring_euri=https%3A%2F%2Fliveseeding.eu%2F&source_ve_path=OTY3MTQ	52